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**Mapping the Landscape of Research on Artificial Intelligence,
Machine Learning, and Deep Learning Applications in COVID-19
Detection: A Web of Science Analysis**

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Abstract

Purpose: The objective the present research study was to draw the landscape of AI, ML, and DL applications in COVID-19 detection by examining the quantity, quality, and structural indicators of publications listed in the ISI Web of Science. **Design, Methodology, Approach:** The study's objectives were attained by extracting data from the ISI Web of Science (WOS) database, followed by deep cleaning using Endnote and manual verification. Biblioshiny and VOSviewer tools were utilized to evaluate the refined data, covering both quantitative and qualitative dimensions. This comprehensive analysis included examining publication output, citation metrics, and country-specific productivity, as well as assessing citation impact through indicators like h-index, g-index, and m-index. Moreover, the study assessed conformity to Bradford's Law and Lotka's Law, and visualized research trends, collaborations, and thematic clusters. **Findings:** The study's findings show that a significant number of articles were co-authored. The most networked author belonged to Hong Kong. China leads in terms of output, influence, and collaboration. IEEE Access and Computers in Biology and Medicine remained the most prominent source for papers on the phenomenon under investigation. **Originality Value:** The research is the first to identify the amount (frequency), quality (impact), and structural indicators (correlations) of AI/ML/DL in COVID-identification. The results hold significant importance for scholars and nations seeking to enhance their comprehension of the phenomena of artificial intelligence, machine learning, deep learning, and COVID-19 detection. The results are also beneficial to the authors and nations hoping to increase international research collaboration.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Machine Learning; Deep Learning; Research on Covid-19 Detection; Bradford Law; Lotka Law; Bibliometric Analysis; Informetric Analysis.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) was initiated as a discipline by John McCarthy and publicized at a conference at Dartmouth College in Hanover, New Hampshire, in 1956 (Dhamija and Bag, 2020). It is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines that may behave like humans. AI has so impacted our daily lives that we hardly notice it. For instance, we use Google in everyday life, and it retrieves results based on its AI. We barely notice its backend functioning IE (Omar, 2022, Trajkovski, 2014). Moreover, Facebook shows advertisements of one's interest in their feeds (Hussain et al., 2022). Ceron (2019) further elaborated that anything mimicking human behavior is AI. It has a subset, namely machine learning (ML), that focuses on getting machines to decide by feeding them data. Arthur Samuel coined the concept of machine learning right after the invention of AI in 1959 (Samuel, 1967). There is a subset of machine learning called deep learning (DL). It uses neural networks to solve extremely complex problems. In simple terms, both of the subsets provide data, algorithms, and neural networks to AI to solve complex problems. Deep learning algorithms are intelligent enough to adapt themselves from situation to situation. "The earliest computer-based model of a neural network was developed in 1943 by Walter Pitts and Warren McCulloch, is where the idea of deep learning initially emerged" (Foote, 2022). Though older, recent researchers call it a subset of AI. The AI and its subsets can be understood through the following figure:

Figure 1: Artificial intelligence and its subsets adapted from Ceron (2019)

Initially, the use of AI, ML, and DL could be traced in the domain of healthcare (Jain et al., 2021a, Pee et al., 2019).

Literature Review and Identification of Research Gap

At the beginning of the twenty-first century, scholars became interested in the ideas of AI, ML, and DL (Aristodemou and Tietze, 2018, Chah, 2019, Mounts, 2021). The concept has been researched in the disciplines of business (Wang et al., 2022, Mikalef et al., 2021); education (Kharbat et al., 2021, Lameris and Arnab, 2022); library and information management (Yao et al., 2015); marketing (Stone et al., 2020) and healthcare, which is perhaps one of the most AI impacted disciplines in the form of healthcare robotics (Pee et al., 2019); predictive medicine (Rodriguez, 2021); mobile applications for mental healthcare (Gamble, 2020); and deep medicine (Hagen, 2019). Along with these AI healthcare dimensions, AI played a crucial role in the coronavirus outbreak when the virus hit the world in December 2019. The epidemic massively increased; 587 million confirmed cases and 6.4 million deaths were reported till August 14, 2022 (WHO, 2022). The AI has been researched and used in the context of detection of COVID-19 detection (Verde et al., 2021, Alsharif et al., 2020); Alsharif et al., 2020); radiography of COVID-19 patients (Carlile et al., 2020); lung CT (Belfiore et al., 2020); and even predicting the mortality of COVID-19 patients admitted to hospitals (Ko et al., 2020). The literature review conducted for the present investigation indicated that there was no paper published so far on the quantity, quality, and structure of literature related to the usage of AI, ML, and DL learning for the detection of COVID-19.

The literature indicated that the technique used for calculating these types indicators is called bibliometric analysis and is popular among researchers (Awan and Abbas, 2022, Lewison, 2001, Nwagwu, 2006). Therefore, this bibliometric study is designed in a comprehensive way to indicate the AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection-related quantity (number of articles, authors, journals, and countries), quality (most impactful articles, authors, journals, and countries), and structural (which information source was favored by authors from which countries) indicators of the research indexed in the ISI Web of Science database.

Research Questions

The following research questions were devised to identify the patterns of literature indexed in the ISI WoS database and related to AI, ML, DL and COVID-19 detection:

RQ1. What are the dominant document types, authorship patterns, and citation trends in AI/ML/DL research on COVID-19 detection?

RQ2. How have publication and citation trends in AI/ML/DL research on COVID-19 detection evolved over time (2019-August 2022)?

RQ3. Which publications on AI/ML/DL research in COVID-19 detection have received the most citations between 2019 and August 2022?

RQ4. What are the growth trends of information sources (journals, conferences, etc.) publishing AI/ML/DL research on COVID-19 detection from 2019 to August 2022?

RQ5. How do top authors, countries, and journals collaborate and contribute to AI/ML/DL research in COVID-19 detection, and what are the underlying dynamics of research output and collaboration?

Methods

The bibliometric analysis technique was used to conduct this study. Bibliometric studies are common in library and information management, and researchers have previously used them to map the published literature (Xu et al., 2021, Cooper et al., 2021, Ortega, 2019, Fiala and Willett, 2015, Qiaoli et al., 2015).

An advanced search string was devised to extract data from ISI WoS using Boolean operators and wild-card. The term detect was searched in the thesaurus to find its synonyms. The relevant synonyms were added to the search string. The search string is as follows: (((TI=(artificial intelligence or machine learning or deep learning or robot*)) AND TI=(covid* or corona)) AND TI=(detect* or ident* or test* or ident* or spot*)). This string retrieved 416 results in the WoS core collections. Rogers et al. (2020), in their paper on sample sizes in the bibliometric studies, suggested 200 papers analytical minimum. Larger than this set of criteria, the researcher decided to analyse 416 records. These records were downloaded in RIS and Bibtex format for further analysis.

Data Cleaning

Literature indicates three data cleaning techniques used: a) excluding early cited papers, b) verifying the number of papers through human eye verification opening files in MS Excel, and c) duplication-checking in Endnote software (Awan and Abbas, 2022). In the case of the present investigation, the early access/cite papers were not excluded because there were already few citable years for the literature published related to the under consideration phenomenon. The records, however, were visually inspected and duplication checked in Endnote software. Both these practices ensured no faulty record. These 416 records were analyzed further.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Main Information about the Data

Description		
<i>Main Information About Data</i>	Timespan	2018:2022
	Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	214
	Documents	416
	Annual Growth Rate %	242.12

	Document Average Age	0.799
	Average citations per doc	15.69
	References	11366
<i>Document Contents</i>	Keywords Plus (ID)	307
	Author's Keywords (DE)	912
<i>Authors</i>	Authors	2186
	Authors of single-authored docs	18
<i>Authors Collaboration</i>	Single-authored docs	18
	Co-Authors per Doc	5.89
	International co-authorships %	41.35
<i>Document Types</i>	Article	358
	Article; early access	20
	Correction	2
	Editorial material	2
	Letter	3
	Meeting abstract	11
	Review	18
	Review; early access	2

The key facts regarding the data are shown in Table 1. So far, 214 sources have published 416 documents about AI/ML/DL in COVID-19 detection. The period from 2018 to 2022 saw the mostly publication of this tenure in the form of articles. The papers on AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection were impactful and secured an average of 15.69 citations. Most cloud computing documents (N = 358) are articles, followed by articles for early access (N = 20) and editorial content (N = 2). These 419 documents were produced with great intellectual rigour and had 11366 end references. These publications contained 912 keywords. The authorship trends revealed that 2186 authors contributed to the COVID-19 identification as well as the AI, ML, DL, and Covid-19 detection. There were just 18 single-authored documents. The international co-authorship percentage remained at 41.35%. As of August 2022, the documents published on the AI/ML/DL and detection of COVID-19 has the following year-by-year production of documents and citations:

Table 2: Year-wise Production and Impact Statistics

Year	N	MeanTCperArt	MeanTCperYear	CitableYears
2018	1	6.00	1.50	4
2019	0	0.00	0.00	0
2020	55	61.04	30.52	2
2021	201	13.29	13.29	1
2022	137	2.36		0

According to Table 2, from 2018 to 2021, more articles were about AI/ML/DL and COVID-19 detection. It decreased somewhat in 2022, but only because the data from ISI WoS was pulled in August of that year. The year 2020 saw the most citations overall, averaging 61.04 citations per article for the 55 publications published that year.

Table 3: *Most Cited Articles*

Author	Document type	Total Citations	TC per year
Li et al. (2020)	“Using Artificial Intelligence to Detect COVID-19 and Community-acquired Pneumonia Based on Pulmonary CT: Evaluation of the Diagnostic Accuracy”	610	203.33
Panwar et al. (2020b)	“Application of deep learning for fast detection of COVID-19 in X-Rays using nCOVnet”	191	63.67
Togacar et al. (2020)	“COVID-19 detection using deep learning models to exploit Social Mimic Optimization and structured chest X-ray images using fuzzy color and stacking approaches”	191	63.67
Roberts et al. (2021)	“Common pitfalls and recommendations for using machine learning to detect and prognosticate for COVID-19 using chest radiographs and CT scans”	190	95.00
Harmon et al. (2020)	“Artificial intelligence for the detection of COVID-19 pneumonia on chest CT using multinational datasets”	183	61.00
Ismael and Sengur (2021)	“Deep learning approaches for COVID-19 detection based on chest X-ray images”	182	91.00
Loey et al. (2020)	“Within the Lack of Chest COVID-19 X-ray Dataset: A Novel Detection Model Based on GAN and Deep Transfer Learning”	171	57.00
Brunese et al. (2020)	“Explainable Deep Learning for Pulmonary Disease and Coronavirus COVID-19 Detection from X-rays”	168	56.00
Loey et al. (2021)	“A hybrid deep transfer learning model with machine learning methods for face mask detection in the era of the COVID-19 pandemic”	164	82.00
Rao and Vazquez (2020)	“Identification of COVID-19 can be quicker through artificial intelligence framework using a mobile phone-based survey when cities and towns are under quarantine”	140	46.67
Hu et al. (2020)	“Weakly Supervised Deep Learning for COVID-19 Infection Detection and Classification from CT Images”	133	44.33
Jain et al. (2021b)	“Deep learning based detection and analysis of COVID-19 on chest X-ray images”	114	57.00

Panwar et al. (2020a)	“A deep learning and grad-CAM based color visualisation approach for fast detection of COVID-19 cases using chest X-ray and CT-Scan images”	106	35.33
Rajaraman et al. (2020)	“Iteratively Pruned Deep Learning Ensembles for COVID-19 Detection in Chest X-Rays”	98	32.67
Brinati et al. (2020)	“Detection of COVID-19 Infection from Routine Blood Exams with Machine Learning: A Feasibility Study”	96	32.00
Albahri et al. (2020a)	“Role of biological Data Mining and Machine Learning Techniques in Detecting and Diagnosing the Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19): A Systematic Review”	96	32.00
Das et al. (2022)	“Automated Deep Transfer Learning Based Approach for Detection of COVID-19 Infection in Chest X-rays”	93	93.00
Ahuja et al. (2021)	“Deep transfer learning-based automated detection of COVID-19 from lung ICT scan slices”	91	45.50
Sedik et al. (2020)	“Deploying Machine and Deep Learning Models for Efficient Data-Augmented Detection of COVID-19 Infections”	86	28.67
Nayak et al. (2021)	“Application of deep learning techniques for detection of COVID-19 cases using chest X-ray images: A comprehensive study”	86	43.00
Albahri et al. (2020b)	“Systematic review of artificial intelligence techniques in the detection and classification of COVID-19 medical images in terms of evaluation and benchmarking: Taxonomy analysis, challenges, future solutions and methodological aspects”	86	28.67

Table 3 indicates that the top article was written by Li et al. (2020). It secured 610 citations and 203.33 total citations per year. In the article, the researcher investigated the use of AI in detecting COVID-19 through CT. Panwar et al. (2020b) and Togacar et al. (2020) authored two equally prominent articles. Both groups of authors worked on fast detecting COVID-19 using deep learning in X-rays. Both articles secured 191 total citations in the two years following their publication. This made the articles and authors secure 63.67 citations per year each. The third most impactful article was authored by Roberts et al. (2021), who secured 190 total citations in one year after publishing his article on COVID-19 detection through machine learning. This article received 95 citations per year.

Figure 2: Sources Growth Graph Year-Wise

Figure 2 indicates the growth of the sources from 2018 to 2022. A journal entitled “Computers in Biology and Medicine” has published the most significant number of articles during the year 2022 up to the month of August (N = 18). The publishing trend in it is on the rise. IEEE Access is the second most prominent source, which started publishing in 2020. It is worth mentioning that all the top 20 journals are on the rise in publishing phenomena related to AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. Researchers frequently use the h, g, and m indexes as measurements. A metric at the author level is called the *h*-index. It gauges the output and influence of researchers or articles regarding citations. It is based on the most frequently cited articles and the number of times each article has been cited in other papers (Huang, 2012, Rousseau, 2014, Yaminfiroz and Gholinia, 2015, Bornmann, 2012). It also applies equally to a scholarly journal's output and impact in the form of citations (Jacsó, 2012, Awan and Abbas, 2022). The *g* index serves as the second key metric. It was introduced as an enhancement to Hirsch's *h*-index to gauge how well a group of articles performed globally in terms of citations. The number of combined citations from all of the researcher's works, listed in decreasing order, is used to calculate the *g* index for each article. According to Abramo et al. (2013), Alonso et al. (2010), Rodrigo and María (2008) the primary distinction between the *h* index and the *g* index is that the former is based on the average number of citations received by all of an academic's lifetime articles, while the latter is based on the number of papers receiving citations. As a result of supporting low-cited publications with citations from highly cited articles, the *g* index is typically higher than the *h* index. The *m* index is the third matrix used to distinguish between the degrees of the effect produced by various scholars or publications with various lengths of tenure. Presumably, the *h* index raises with career length and the *g* index raises when some papers receive more and others fewer citations. The *m* index shows the effects based on the lifespan of a publication or the researcher's research career (Bornmann, 2012, Sanyal et al., 2020). The influence of the information sources was calculated for each of the three metrics. The *h*, *g*, and *m* indexes, as well as the total number of citations and the year the information source first appeared, are shown in

Table 4.

Table 4: Sources impact through H, G and M indexes calculations

Sr. No.	Element	H Index	G index	M index	PY		
					TC	NP	start
1	IEEE Access	8	15	2.66	409	15	2020
2	Computers in Biology & Medicine	7	16	2.33	334	16	2020
3	PLOS One	6	8	2	72	10	2020
4	Applied Intelligence	5	5	2.5	268	5	2021
5	Expert Systems with Applications	5	6	2.5	229	6	2021
6	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	5	6	1.66	163	6	2020
7	Applied Soft Computing	4	5	2	115	5	2021
8	Biomedical Signal Processing and Control	4	6	2	162	6	2021
9	Chaos Soitons & Fractals	4	4	1.33	429	4	2020
10	Diagnostics	4	7	1.33	86	7	2020
11	Journal of Medical Internet Research	4	4	1.33	45	4	2020
12	Applied Sciences-basel	3	6	1.5	36	6	2021
13	Cmc-computers Materials & Continua	3	5	1.5	60	5	2021
14	Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine	3	3	1.5	16	3	2021
15	International Journal of Imaging Systems and Technology	3	3	1.5	13	5	2021
16	Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing	3	3		14	3	
17	Journal of Healthcare Engineering	3	4	1.5	37	4	2021
18	Journal of Medical Systems	3	3	1	219	3	2020
19	Neural Computing & Applications	3	3		98	3	
20	Scientific Reports	3	7	1.5	56	7	2021
	Sensors	3	8	1.5	90	8	2021

The top 20 sources from 2018 to August 2022 that published content on AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection are included in Table 4. "IEEE Access" started in 2020, and it indicated the highest total citations of 409 (h = 8; g = 15; m = 2.66). The second-highest number of citations overall (334) was secured by "Computers in Biology & Medicine" (h = 7; m = 2.33). However, this journal displayed the highest g-index (g = 16). PLOS One ranked third among the most impactful journals (h = 6, g = 8, and m = 2). The first publications about the topic under study appeared in each of these periodicals in 2020. The next measure taken was Bradford's law. The rule is often referred to as the Pareto distribution, Bradford distribution, or Bradford law of scattering. An illustration of the law would be if a researcher discovered five main journals and ten articles of interest in each.

Moreover, if the researcher wants another ten papers of interest, he or she will need to check out ten more journals (first nucleus number of articles multiplied by two). The researcher will have to screen 20 publications in this course to discover ten more articles (again multiplied by two). The researcher will eventually realize there is no sense in continuing their quest (Alabi, 1979; Bradford, 1934; Hjrland and Nicolaisen, 2005

Figure 3: Distribution of journals according to the Bradford's law

Figure 3 indicates that journals are distributed precisely, as Bradford (1934) described. According to the Bradford law, the journals, namely "Computers in Biology and Medicine" (N = 18), "IEEE Access" (N = 15), "Scientific Reports" (N = 11), and "PLoS ONE" (N = 10) were the core nucleus publications connected to the concept of AI, ML, DL, and Covid-19 detection. Figure 2 depicts the state of the other journals very succinctly. A co-authorship map of authors was created, setting a threshold of the maximum of 25 authors per document and the minimum number of authors for a document to two. The authorship map was produced after 190 out of 2153 authors met the cut-off.

Figure 4: Co-Authorship Map

Vardhanabhuti, V., remained at the top of the co-authorship strength patterns heatmap with a link strength (total number of partnerships) of 43. He wrote four documents. S. Chakraborty and MA Khan created four documents but did not work jointly with anyone. The remaining authors on the map each produced three or two documents. To understand the research trends in the fields of AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 identification, co-occurrences of authors' keywords were mapped. At least two keyword occurrences were selected as the minimum. Only 251 of the 1076 keywords met the requirement. The following is the map that shows the map and the link strength among the keywords:

Figure 5: Keywords Heat Map Indicating Associated Research Trends With Artificial Intelligence

The 251 keyword repetitions of COVID-19 had the highest connection strength at 1166, followed by 156 instances of deep learning, with total link strength of 784, and 80 instances of machine learning, with total link strength of 403.

Lotka (1926) provided a law to measure the productivity of authors. It is well-known among academics because it is one of the fundamental laws of Informetric. Its creator claimed that making x contributions in a certain amount of time are a fraction of making a single contribution. According to Maz-Machado et al. (2017) and other writers, the rule has a probability distribution that shows how productive an author is in a field and the link between an author and the number of articles they publish.

Figure 5: Authors' productivity according to Lotka's law

Lotka's law proved true in the case of the present bibliometric investigation, where 1926 researchers contributed by writing 1 document each, while one researcher authored seven articles. Fourteen authors wrote four documents each, and 24 wrote three. The analysis showed that 144 authors wrote two documents, while a sizable percentage of authors ($N = 1926$) contributed one article. Each of the 24 authors contributed three documents. Seven documents by one author were discovered. According to earlier authors' descriptions of Lotka's law, the number of author's decreases as the number of articles rises. This remained the same in the present case another crucial quantitative measure related to Informetric research is estimating each country's research output. It shows the number of articles that originated from a country.

Therefore, it was determined how productive countries were in terms of AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. The country's productivity is visible in the following figure:

Figure 6: Countries' Total Production

Figure 6 displays the research output in AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. With 295 articles, China leads the productivity index, followed by India with 238 documents. With 224 documents, the United States of America placed third in productivity. Saudi Arabia stayed in fourth place with 123, followed by the UK with 99, Italy with 68, Australia with

66, Iran with 64, Egypt with 62, Turkey with 58, Germany with 55, Pakistan with 52, and South Korea with 50. The impact of the countries is shown in the following graph:

Figure 7: Countries' Impact

The total number of citations discovered by the countries is depicted in Figure 7. China remained the most productive and frequently quoted nation. China received 1171 citations, with an average article citation of 27.88. The USA came in second with 777 total citations and 21 citations per piece. India maintained its third-place ranking with 741 citations and an average of 11.23 citations per piece. Calculating the average number of citations per piece reveals a very different picture. Mexico, which had 314 citations, has the most significant average number of citations per article (N = 62.80). Vietnam came in second with 43 average article citations and 43 citations, followed by Norway with 55 average article citations. India came in at number 21, the USA at 11, and China at 6 in terms of average article citations.

Figure 8: Three fields plot of authors, countries, and their preferred journals

A three-field plot was created by researching the top 20 authors, their countries, and the information sources in which they have published. The results of the three field plots show Chinese authors' highest contributions. In total, 18 top Chinese authors were published in

9 different sources. Five Indian authors published in 13 information sources, and ten Saudi Arabian authors also published in 13 information sources. Computers in Biology and Medicine published articles from scattered geographic locations in 15 countries, followed by IEEE Access, publishing documents from 14 countries. Zhang, S. from China, Abdul Kareem, and Al-Waisy from Iraqi origin contributed six papers each.

Discussion

A total of 416 documents were taken out of the ISI WoS database related to AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. Every time a phenomenon arises in literature, Awan and Abbas (2022) have previously noted that it is initially presented at conferences. Finally, it finds a home in peer-reviewed journals. This was not true during the current study. Articles comprised the highest number of documents (N = 358), followed by early cite articles (N = 20). This may have occurred because COVID-19 was a pandemic, and researchers did not want to present their papers linked to the AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection in conferences or because conferences were locked down during COVID-19 and switched to online mode. No conference paper linked to the phenomenon under examination was discovered, regardless of the circumstance.

The number of papers discussing AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection has increased since the concept's inception in 2020. There was no total number of documents decreased between August 2020 and August 2022. If we consider the topic as a product, it is growing in 2022 after the initial stage of 2020, as happens in the form of the information cycle (Armstrong et al., 2014, Kotler, 2017).

The most overall citations (N = 610) and total citations per year (N = 203.33) were obtained by Li et al. (2020). Panwar et al. (2020) and Togacar et al. (2020) came in second in total citation counts (N = 191). Roberts et al. (2021) stood third, whose total citation count remained 190. The first authors were at the top in total citations and year-wise publications. However, in the yearly citations count, the authors in numbers two and three differed from those with the highest total citations. Das et al. (2022) earned the second-highest number of yearly citations (N = 93), and Ismael and Sengur (2021) earned the third-highest yearly citations (N = 91).

The highest publishing journal as of 2022, "Computers in Biology and Medicine," published 29 papers. Even if "IEEE Access" did not publish the most publications in 2022 (N= 36), it published the most significant number of articles from 2020 to 2022. Additionally growing, "PLOS ONE" has published a total of 21 papers in its account.

IEEE Access is the journal with the highest h and m indices. Computers in biology and medicine achieved the highest g index. These journals may be consulted by upcoming researchers working in AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. Libraries may decide to subscribe to the publications for their users also. These results support the prior claim made by Awan and Abbas (2022) that each quality metric has its benefits. An item with a high h index may or may not be connected to high m or g indices. The data analysis section includes a list of the top 20 journals that publish articles on AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection.

However, as of 2022, "Computers in Biology and Medicine" is the journal that publishes most documents relevant to AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. The second-most frequently published journal concerning the phenomena of AI, ML, DL, and

COVID-19 detection is IEEE Access.

Bradford's law shows relevant journals to the area of interest. In the instance of the current investigation, the Bradford law stayed unchanged. The journals enlisted in the present investigation can be split into three categories. According to the Bradford law, the first four sources (or the nucleus) had published 103 articles. The next eight sources (early 4 multiplied by 2) resulted in the publication of 101 articles. The next 12 sources had published 100 articles. Researchers interested in AI, L, DL, and COVID-19 identification should take note of these intriguing discoveries. By locating the core journals for any field of study, their research may become simple and easy by keeping Bradford's law in mind. The majority of the articles that the researchers will need can be found in nucleus journals by reviewing these core publications in their area of expertise. This Bradford law is generalizable to other areas of studies also.

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China is the country with the highest production ($N = 295$) and citation ($N = 1171$) rates, making it the expert in the world in terms of AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 identification. The strongest network of co-authorship collaborations was maintained by the author from Hong Kong, the USA, and Saudi Arabia. The authors from less productive countries or continents who want to undertake research in collaboration with other authors or nations can get in touch with the massively networked writers indicated in Figure 3 for collaborations.

According to research trends, convolutional neural networks, prediction, models, and computer-aided diagnosis are associated with the majority of research on AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. The importance of "radiology" and "chest x-rays" in the detection of COVID-19 has gained the attention of researchers (Rajaraman et al., 2020a, 2020b, Saiz and Barandiaran, 2020, Alghamdi et al., 2021). (Ghaderzadeh and Asadi, 2021).

Conclusion

The study examined the productivity of research concerning the ideas of AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. Articles made up most documents overall. In 2020, the phenomenon of AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection began to take off, and it continued to grow until 2022. Additionally, the citations had a normal trend to rise as the number of citable years rose. The articles produced in 2020 have the most citations overall per piece. A paper on the topic of applying artificial intelligence to spot COVID-19 was published in 2020 by Li et al. It continued to be the most often quoted piece from the under investigation era. Compared to the other journals, "IEEE Access" published far more papers.

This journal had the greatest influence in terms of total citations, h index, and m index. "Computers in Biology and Medicine," "IEEE Access," "Scientific Reports," and "PLOS ONE" were the main journals that published the majority of the literature on AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. Hong Kong authors dominated authorship trends. Vardhanabhuti, a writer of Hong Kong ancestry, continued to be the leading co-authored researcher. The second and third most connected authors were Chakraborti from the USA and Khan from Saudi Arabia.

The most often used keyword was still COVID-19, which was followed by deep learning and machine learning. According to the data, just one author has written as many articles as seven. This analysis validated Bradford's law, which states that core journals often include the majority of the readership-relevant articles. It was established that Lotka's law, which states that the number of authors decreases as the number of articles increases, is also accurate in the context of the present investigation. China is the most productive nation and continues to have the most significant influence. The USA continued to be the second most productive and influential nation in terms of AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection.

However, Chinese authors are unique because they have published in a wide range of 18 prestigious sources that publish research articles on AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection.

Limitation of the Study

A software-based method for data extraction and analysis is bibliometric analysis. Although the writers properly cleaned and extracted the data and verified it with the human eye, there can be little data extraction inaccuracy because of artificial intelligence-based data extraction.

Directions for the Future Research

Future bibliometric research may be conducted to assess the production of various nations separately, journals, and their respective collaboration maps concerning AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection. Additionally, using bibliometric studies, it is possible to assess productivity among continents and nations in relation to the concepts of AI, ML, DL, and COVID-19 detection.

References

- Abramo, G., D'Angelo, C.A. and Viel, F., 2013. The suitability of h and g indexes for measuring the research performance of institutions. *Scientometrics*, 97, pp.555-570.
- Albahri, A.S., Hamid, R.A., Alwan, J.K., Al-Qays, Z.T., Zaidan, A.A., Zaidan, B.B., Albahri, A.O.S., AlAmoodi, A.H., Khlaf, J.M., Almahdi, E.M. and Thabet, E., 2020. Role of biological data mining and machine learning techniques in detecting and diagnosing the novel coronavirus (COVID-19): a systematic review. *Journal of medical systems*, 44, pp.1-11.
- Albahri, O.S., Zaidan, A.A., Albahri, A.S., Zaidan, B.B., Abdulkareem, K.H., Al-Qaysi, Z.T., AlAmoodi, A.H., Aleesa, A.M., Chyad, M.A., Alesa, R.M. and Lim, C.K., 2020. Systematic review of artificial intelligence techniques in the detection and classification of COVID-19 medical images in terms of evaluation and benchmarking: Taxonomy analysis, challenges, future solutions and methodological aspects. *Journal of infection and public health*, 13(10), pp.1381-1396.

- Alonso, S., Cabrerizo, F., Herrera-Viedma, E. and Herrera, F., 2010. hg-index: A new index to characterize the scientific output of researchers based on the h-and g-indices. *Scientometrics*, 82(2), pp.391-400.
- Alsharif, M.H., Alsharif, Y.H., Chaudhry, S.A., Albreem, M.A., Jahid, A. and Hwang, E., 2020. Artificial intelligence technology for diagnosing COVID-19 cases: A review of substantial issues. *European review for medical and pharmacological sciences*.
- Aristodemou, L. and Tietze, F., 2018. The state-of-the-art on Intellectual Property Analytics (IPA): A literature review on artificial intelligence, machine learning and deep learning methods for analysing intellectual property (IP) data. *World Patent Information*, 55, pp.37-51.
- Awan, W.A. and Abbas, A., 2023. Mapping the quantity, quality and structural indicators of Asian (48 countries and 3 territories) research productivity on cloud computing. *Library Hi Tech*, 41(2), pp.309-332.
- Belfiore, M.P., Urraro, F., Grassi, R., Giacobbe, G., Patelli, G., Cappabianca, S. and Reginelli, A., 2020. Artificial intelligence to codify lung CT in Covid-19 patients. *La radiologia medica*, 125, pp.500-504.
- Bornmann, L., 2012. Redundancies in h index variants and the proposal of the number of top-cited papers as an attractive indicator. *Measurement: Interdisciplinary Research and Perspectives*, 10(3), pp.149-153.
- Brinati, D., Campagner, A., Ferrari, D., Locatelli, M., Banfi, G. and Cabitza, F., 2020. Detection of COVID-19 infection from routine blood exams with machine learning: a feasibility study. *Journal of medical systems*, 44, pp.1-12.
- Brunese, L., Mercaldo, F., Reginelli, A. and Santone, A., 2020. Explainable deep learning for pulmonary disease and coronavirus COVID-19 detection from X-rays. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 196, p.105608.
- Carlile, M., Hurt, B., Hsiao, A., Hogarth, M., Longhurst, C.A. and Dameff, C., 2020. Deployment of artificial intelligence for radiographic diagnosis of COVID-19 pneumonia in the emergency department. *JACEP Open*, 1(6), pp.1459-1464.
- Ceron, R. (2019), "AI, machine learning and deep learning: What's the difference", IBM IT Infrastructure Blog. <https://www.ibm.com/blogs/systems/ai-machine>
- Chah, N., 2019. Down the deep rabbit hole: Untangling deep learning from machine learning and artificial intelligence. *First Monday*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 1-1.
- Cooper, T., Aharony, N. and Bar-Ilan, J. (2021), "Gender differences in the Israeli academia: a bibliometric analysis of different disciplines", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 73 No. 2, pp. 160-179.
- Das, N. N., Kumar, N., Kaur, M., Kumar, V. and Singh, D. (2022), "Automated Deep Transfer Learning- Based Approach for Detection of COVID-19 Infection in Chest X-rays", *IRBM*, Vol. 43 No. 2, pp. 114-119.
- Dhamija, P. and Bag, S. (2020), "Role of artificial intelligence in operations environment: a review and bibliometric analysis", *The TQM Journal*, Vol. 32 No. 4, pp. 869-896.
- Fiala, D. and Willett, P. (2015), "Computer science in Eastern Europe 1989-2014: a bibliometric study", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 67 No. 5, pp. 526-541.
- Foote, K. D. (2022), "A Brief History of Deep Learning".

- Gamble, A., 2020. Artificial intelligence and mobile apps for mental healthcare: a social informatics perspective. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 72(4), pp.509-523.
- Hagen, J. B. (2019), "Deep medicine: how artificial intelligence can make healthcare human again", *Choice: Current Reviews for Academic Libraries*, Vol. 56 No. 11, pp. 1383-1383.
- Harmon, S.A., Sanford, T.H., Xu, S., Turkbey, E.B., Roth, H., Xu, Z., Yang, D., Myronenko, A., Anderson, V., Amalou, A. and Blain, M., 2020. Artificial intelligence for the detection of COVID-19 pneumonia on chest CT using multinational datasets. *Nature communications*, 11(1), p.4080.
- Hu, S. P., Gao, Y., Niu, Z. M., Jiang, Y. H., Li, L., Xiao, X. L., Wang, M. H., Fang, E. F., Menpes-Smith, W., Xia, J., Ye, H. and Yang, G. (2020), "Weakly Supervised Deep Learning for COVID-19 Infection Detection and Classification From CT Images", *IEEE ACCESS*, Vol. 8, pp. 118869-118883.
- Huang, M.-H. (2012), "Exploring the h-index at the institutional levelA practical application in world university rankings", *Online Information Review*, Vol. 36 No. 4, pp. 534-547.
- Hussain, Z., Sheikh, Z., Tahir, A., Dashtipour, K., Gogate, M., Sheikh, A. and Hussain, A. (2022), "Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Social Media Analysis for Pharmacovigilance of COVID-19 Vaccinations in the United Kingdom: Observational Study", *JMIR PUBLIC HEALTH AND SURVEILLANCE*, Vol. 8 No. 5.
- Ismael, A. M. and Sengur, A. (2021), "Deep learning approaches for COVID-19 detection based on chest X-ray images", *EXPERT SYSTEMS WITH APPLICATIONS*, Vol. 164.
- Jacsó, P. (2012), "Google Scholar Metrics for Publications", *Online Information Review*, Vol. 36 No. 4, pp. 604-619.
- Jain, M., Goel, A., Sinha, S. and Dhir, S. (2021a), "Employability implications of artificial intelligence in healthcare ecosystem: responding with readiness", *foresight*, Vol. 23 No. 1, pp. 73-94.
- Jain, R., Gupta, M., Taneja, S. and Hemanth, D. J. (2021b), "Deep learning based detection and analysis of COVID-19 on chest X-ray images", *APPLIED INTELLIGENCE*, Vol. 51 No. 3, pp. 1690-1700.
- Kharbat, F. F., Alshawabkeh, A. and Woolsey, M. L. (2021), "Identifying gaps in using artificial intelligence to support students with intellectual disabilities from education and health perspectives", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 73 No. 1, pp. 101-128.
- Ko, H., Chung, H., Kang, W. S., Kim, K. W., Shin, Y., Kang, S. J., Lee, J. H., Kim, Y. J., Kim, N. Y., Jung, H. and Lee, J. (2020), "COVID-19 Pneumonia Diagnosis Using a Simple 2D Deep Learning Framework With a Single Chest CT Image: Model Development and Validation", *JOURNAL OF MEDICAL INTERNET RESEARCH*, Vol. 22 No. 6.
- Lameras, P. and Arnab, S. (2022), "Power to the Teachers: An Exploratory Review on Artificial Intelligence in Education", *Information (2078-2489)*, Vol. 13 No. 1, pp. 14-N.PAG.
- Lewis, G. (2001), "The quantity and quality of female researchers: a bibliometric study of Iceland", pp. 29-43.
- Li, L., Qin, L. X., Xu, Z. G., Yin, Y. B., Wang, X., Kong, B., Bai, J. J., Lu, Y., Fang, Z. H., Song, Q., Cao, K. L., Liu, D. L., Wang, G. S., Xu, Q. Z., Fang, X. S., Zhang, S. Q.,

- Xia, J. and Xia, J. (2020), "Using Artificial Intelligence to Detect COVID-19 and Community-acquired Pneumonia Based on Pulmonary CT: Evaluation of the Diagnostic Accuracy", *RADIOLOGY*, Vol. 296 No. 2, pp. E65.
- Loey, M., Manogaran, G., Taha, M. H. N. and Khalifa, N. E. M. (2021), "A hybrid deep transfer learning model with machine learning methods for face mask detection in the era of the COVID-19 pandemic", *MEASUREMENT*, Vol. 167.
- Loey, M., Smarandache, F. and Khalifa, N. E. M. (2020), "Within the Lack of Chest COVID-19 X-ray Dataset: A Novel Detection Model Based on GAN and Deep Transfer Learning", *SYMMETRY-BASEL*, Vol. 12 No. 4.
- Mikalef, P., Pappas, I. O., Krogstie, J., Jaccheri, L. and Rana, N. (2021), "Editors' reflections and introduction to the special section on 'Artificial Intelligence and Business Value'", *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 57, pp. N.PAG-N.PAG.
- Mounts, M. (2021), "Artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning", *Choice: Current Reviews for Academic Libraries*, Vol. 58 No. 5, pp. 484-484.
- Nayak, S. R., Nayak, D. R., Sinha, U., Arora, V. and Pachori, R. B. (2021), "Application of deep learning techniques for detection of COVID-19 cases using chest X-ray images: A comprehensive study", *BIOMEDICAL SIGNAL PROCESSING AND CONTROL*, Vol. 64.
- Nwagwu, W. E. (2006), "BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF QUANTITY AND QUALITY OF NIGERIA'S BIOMEDICAL LITERATURE", *LIBRES: Library & Information Science Research Electronic Journal*, Vol. 16 No. 2, pp. 1-23
- Omar, A. (2022), "Discourse-based Opinion Mining of Customer Responses to Telecommunications Services in Saudi Arabia during the COVID-19 Crisis", *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED COMPUTER SCIENCE AND APPLICATIONS*, Vol. 13 No. 6, pp. 337-345.
- Ortega, J. L. (2019), "Exploratory analysis of Publons metrics and their relationship with bibliometric and altmetric impact", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 71 No. 1, pp. 124-136.
- Panwar, H., Gupta, P. K., Siddiqui, M. K., Morales-Menendez, R., Bhardwaj, P. and Singh, V. (2020a), "A deep learning and grad-CAM based color visualization approach for fast detection of COVID-19 cases using chest X-ray and CT-Scan images", *CHAOS SOLITONS & FRACTALS*, Vol. 140
- Panwar, H., Gupta, P. K., Siddiqui, M. K., Morales-Menendez, R. and Singh, V. (2020b), "Application of deep learning for fast detection of COVID-19 in X-Rays using nCOVnet", *CHAOS SOLITONS & FRACTALS*, Vol. 138.
- Pee, L. G., Pan, S. L. and Cui, L. (2019), "Artificial intelligence in healthcare robots: A social informatics study of knowledge embodiment", *Journal of the Association for Information Science & Technology*, Vol. 70 No. 4, pp. 351-369.
- Qiaoli, Z., Xuesong, K., Song, H., Junli, L. and Zongyi, H. (2015), "Global ontology research progress: a bibliometric analysis", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 67 No. 1, pp. 27-54.
- Rajaraman, S., Siegelman, J., Alderson, P. O., Folio, L. S., Folio, L. R. and Antani, S. K. (2020), "Iteratively Pruned Deep Learning Ensembles for COVID-19 Detection in

- Chest X-Rays", *IEEE ACCESS*, Vol. 8, pp. 115041-115050.
- Rao, A. and Vazquez, J. A. (2020), "Identification of COVID-19 can be quicker through artificial intelligence framework using a mobile phone-based survey when cities and towns are under quarantine", *INFECTION CONTROL AND HOSPITAL EPIDEMIOLOGY*, Vol. 41 No. 7, pp. 826-830.
- Roberts, M., Driggs, D., Thorpe, M., Gilbey, J., Yeung, M. C., Ursprung, S., Aviles-Rivero, A. I., Etmann, C., McCague, C., Beer, L., Weir-McCall, J. R., Teng, Z. Z., Gkrania-Klotsas, E., Rudd, J. H. F., Sala, E., Schonlieb, C. B. and Aix, C. (2021), "Common pitfalls and recommendations for using machine learning to detect and prognosticate for COVID-19 using chest radiographs and CT scans", *NATURE MACHINE INTELLIGENCE*, Vol. 3 No. 3, pp. 199-217.
- Rodriguez, R. (2021), "Predictive medicine: artificial intelligence and its impact on health care business strategy", *Choice: Current Reviews for Academic Libraries*, Vol. 58 No. 8, pp. 791-791.
- Rogers, G., Szomszor, M. and Adams, J. (2020), "Sample size in bibliometric analysis", *Scientometrics*, Vol. 125 No. 1, pp. 777-794.
- Rousseau, R. (2014), "A note on the interpolated or real-valued h-index with a generalization for fractional counting", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 66 No. 1, pp. 2-12.
- Samuel, A. L. (1967), "Some studies in machine learning using the game of checkers. II—Recent progress", *IBM Journal of research and development*, Vol. 11 No. 6, pp. 601-617.
- Sanyal, D. K., Dey, S. and Das, P. P. (2020), "gm-index: a new mentorship index for researchers", *Scientometrics*, Vol. 123 No. 1, pp. 71-102.
- Sedik, A., Iliyasu, A. M., Abd El-Rahiem, B., Abdel Samea, M. E., Abdel-Raheem, A., Hammad, M., Peng, J. L., Abd El-Samie, F. E. and Abd El-Latif, A. A. (2020), "Deploying Machine and Deep Learning Models for Efficient Data-Augmented Detection of COVID-19 Infections", *VIRUSES-BASEL*, Vol. 12 No. 7.
- Stone, M., Aravopoulou, E., Ekinici, Y., Evans, G., Hobbs, M., Labib, A., Laughlin, P., Machtynger, J. and Machtynger, L. (2020), "Artificial intelligence (AI) in strategic marketing decision-making: a research agenda", *Bottom Line*, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 183-200.
- Togacar, M., Ergen, B. and Comert, Z. (2020), "COVID-19 detection using deep learning models to exploit Social Mimic Optimization and structured chest X-ray images using fuzzy color and stacking approaches", *COMPUTERS IN BIOLOGY AND MEDICINE*, Vol. 121.
- Trajkovski, G. (2014), "Robots are people too: how Siri, Google Car, and artificial intelligence will force us to change our laws", *Choice: Current Reviews for Academic Libraries*, Vol. 51 No. 11, pp. 2003-2004.
- Verde, L., De Pietro, G., Ghoneim, A., Alrashoud, M., Al-Mutib, K. N. and Sannino, G. (2021), Exploring the Use of Artificial Intelligence Techniques to Detect the Presence of Coronavirus Covid-19 Through Speech and Voice Analysis", *IEEE ACCESS*, Vol. 9, pp. 65750-65757.
- Wang, Y. C., Tsai, D. J., Yen, L. C., Yao, Y. H., Chiang, T. T., Chiu, C. H., Lin, T. Y., Yeh,

- K. M. and Chang, F. Y. (2022), "Clinical Characteristics of COVID-19 Patients and Application to an Artificial Intelligence System for Disease Surveillance", *JOURNAL OF CLINICAL MEDICINE*, Vol. 11.
- WHO, W. H. O. (2022), "COVID-19 weekly epidemiological update, edition 105, 17 August 2022".
- Xu, M., Gan, D., Pan, T. and Sun, X. (2021), "Trends and characteristics of China's medical informatization policy from 1996 to 2020: a bibliometric analysis", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 73 No. 5, pp. 720-753.
- Yaminfirooz, M. and Gholinia, H. (2015), "Multiple h-index: a new scientometric indicator", *Electronic Library*, Vol. 33 No. 3, pp. 547-556.
- Yao, F., Zhang, C. and Chen, W. (2015), "Smart talking robot Xiaotu: participatory library service based on artificial intelligence", *Library Hi Tech*, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 245-260.